

Study on Challenges of Local Government in India

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Abstract

Local Government is the lowest level of the government in our administration structure, but it plays a very significant role in the governance. As people participation is largely possible in local government. It makes the representative government into a participatory government. Local government is the corner stone of a vibrant Indian Democracy. It plays a very important role in the development of the community. But it faces a lot of challenges over time. At a point of time where local government was not exist in India to today level of development it crossing many pathways. Starting from BALWANT RAI MEHTA COMMITTEE IN 1957 TO L.M. SINGHVI COMMITTEE Report for the revitalization of panchayat raj and recommend for the inclusion of a new chapter into the constitution of India for local government. But according to the environment it need some changes in its model to make a effective governance. This research paper studies some of the important challenges in the local government. This research paper also studies about some important countries local government model that is suited for India to make the local governance even more effective and efficient. This paper combines the challenges and responses to these problems. This research paper is a descriptive and analytical study. The data were collected from secondary sources such as newspaper, journals, books, government websites, and social media.

Keywords: *Panchayat raj, Municipalities, Constitutional amendment, Gram sabha, Participation*

Introduction

Local Government in India is the lowest level of government, next to union and state Government. Starting with the quotes of Mahatma Gandhi, In My Dreams Of A Modern State, Power Will Not Concentrated In A Few Hands.

Local government is the level of public authority that citizens first look to solve their I mediate problems. Local government is the level of government in which the citizen has the most effective opportunity to actively participate in. Since local governance, takes place on a smaller scale and focuses on local issues, it offers more opportunities for direct democracy and civic engagement.

Local Government in India consists of both rural and urban. Rural it is called panchayat raj and in urban it is commonly called municipalities

Panchayat raj institutions is the system of rural administration. It is constituted under 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act 1992 and it came in force on 24th April 1993. Its salient features includes organization of gram sabha, 3-tier panchayat raj at zila, block and village level etc.

Urban local government is constituted under 74th Constitutional Amendment Act 1993 and it came into exist on 1st July 1993. Its salient features includes establishment of 3 kinds of municipalities such as Nagar Panchayat, Municipal Council, Municipal Corporation.

But it often faces many challenges in the effective of its governance.

I want to share here about the challenges in local government and i compare few countries local government model and take up some important features that is suited for India.

Objectives of the Study

- To know about the problems in the local government.
- To compare some countries local governance model that is suited for India, to address the challenges in the governance of local body.

Methodology of the Study

This research paper is a descriptive and analytical study. The data were collected from books, newspapers, journals, government websites, and social media. Based on the review of the sources the suggestions and the conclusion were derived.

Significance of the Study

The real worth of Local Government can be very aptly summed up in the words of Sh. Jawaharlal Nehru, first Prime Minister of India who opined that "India is poor because the villages of India are poor. India will be rich if the villages of India are rich. Panchayats should be given greater power; for we want the villagers to have a greater measure of real swaraj (Self-Government) in their own villages." This study can assist to address some important problems in local governance to make a better benefit in the society.

Discussion

Challenges In Local Government

- Local government depend on state or union for financial aid due to the lack of adequate revenue generation. Local government expenditure as a % of GDP is only 2%. This is er low compared to other major economies like China (11%) and Brazil (7%)
- Most local bodies, both rural and urban are unable to generate adequate funds from their internal sources, and are therefore extremely dependent on external sources for funding. Studies show that around 80% to 95% of revenue is obtained from external sources, particularly state and central government loans and grants.
- Lack of skilled personnel in planning, finance, and service delivery in the local government. In particular Gram Panchayat most of the time elected The President based on the basis of family, caste or religion emotions.
- Lack of public participation in the local government, In India it is only achieve through Gram Sabha and Municipal Council. But it need some reforms.

Responses to the Challenges

1. Cities can lease government land for infrastructure projects and urban development instead of Solding it Permanently, it ensure long term revenue rather than one time sales.

2. United States -Council Manager State

This system works by appoint a professional manager to handle administration, financial works and ensure efficient Governance. The appointed manager is accountable to the elected representatives but he can operate independently without a political influence.

It can be implemented in Metropolitan cities like Mumbai and Chennai to improve governance and also reduce political interference in administration.

3. Brazil -Participatory Budgeting

Some cities in Brazil allow citizens to directly participate in deciding how local budgets are allocated.

It can be implemented in Gram Sabha and Municipal Council meetings instead of only consulting with important stake holders. It can also be implemented with regulation with atleast 1 member from a family participated in the meetings ensure people participation and create a responsibility and transparency.

4. South Africa-ward Committee System

This system allows each ward elects representative who work closely with municipal councils to address local issues, encourage citizen participation at the grassroots level.

It can strengthen the role of ward committees in Indian municipalities. It can be implemented in smart cities to enhance participatory governance and transparency and people have more faith in government policies as their representative was in the decision making.

5. Increase Revenue in Local Government

Property tax is underutilized in India, contributing only 0.2% of GDP Compared to 3% in developed nations. This can be achieved by some models of some countries.

Sweden and Germany model of taxation:

Direct taxation ensures local government have a stable revenue source, reducing dependency on state grants.

Allow cities to collect a small percentage of income tax.

This could work in metro areas like Mumbai, Delhi and Hyderabad.

A local GST collection ensures a economic development in rural and urban areas by collecting a fixed percentage of GST revenue collected within a city to local government.

Conclusion

The changing circumstances require adoption of new technologies and improvement in governance especially in the local government. Our Indian government address the challenges and adopt to some modern models that make our governance efficient and effective. Empowering the local bodies for Local Governance has been one of the most progressive reform since Independence. It has envisioned to place the governing power in the hands of the general populace. Just like every other reform, this one has a few loopholes in it. Nevertheless, if these gaps are removed, the present local governance system and adoption of new models can truly empower the citizens and support the inclusive growth. As India navigates the challenges of rapid urbanization, rural development empowering these diverse local government entities will be vital in ensuring the provision of essential services, infrastructure development, and the enhancement of the overall quality of life for rural and urban residents.

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